

ABOUT THE METHODS OF FORMALIZATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS

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There are mass, serial and single types of production are determined by the coefficient of consolidation of operations at the workplace (GOST 3.1121.84) [1]. Mass production is characterized by a type of highly specialized departments and sections on output, limited and stable for a long period of time range of products. The main objective of planning is to ensure the movement of workpieces on at a given pace of operations. A significant part of the calendar-planned regulations for the type of mass production is sustainable and just laid the basis for the planned regulations of the production lines. Planning is based on the calculation of the rate of release and details of the calculation of interoperable standards groundwork. When a batch type production nomenclature of manufactured products less stable, but still regularly repeated in the release program, the number performed in detail shops operations far exceeds the number of jobs that determines the production of goods parties. [2]

Main planning task in batch production, ensuring periodicity of manufacture products in accordance with the scheduled task. Increasing seriality achieved unification of parts and typed processes [1]. The objective of production planning is to manufacture products on time and uniform loading of production sites for a given production cycle. Each type of production of different methods can be arranged. The main ones are in-line, single party and methods of production. The most effective line method. The set of methods, tools, and principles of organization of the process to form the production planning and control system. Specifically shown what it takes to build a mathematical model of operations.

It is proved that the execution of technological operations connected with the transfer of technological resources on the subject of work in order to change its properties, each of which is determined by the input parameters.

We consider the formalization of violations of state regulatory process parameters. But while all the above refers to existing guests.

It is concluded that the analytical methods of system design management of industrial production lines are based on the construction of states in the phase space trajectories of the objects of labor. The foundation for building effective models of object-technology-driven production processes that describe the motion of objects on the working party from the technological production line which are the foundation of conservation laws that characterize resource transfer process on the subject of work. Development of a detailed description of the subject-Technology managed production process, based on the stochastic mechanism of transfer of technological resources on the subject of work as a result of the impact of the equipment during the execution process step requires the introduction of parameters characterizing the state of the object of labor in the phase technological space[3].

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